

Section 1 of 2

Survey on Change Languages in Ontologies (2023)

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We welcome ontology users (such as biocurators and data scientists), ontology developers and tool builders to participate in our first workshop. You will learn about our Knowledge Graph Change Language (KGCL) and our prototype system for viewing and requesting changes to BioPortal ontologies, and you'll help us gather community requirements and use cases related to communicating ontology changes.

This workshop is now scheduled for 2023-05-09 from 8-11am PT (11am-3pm ET). To register, please fill out all of the required questions and as many of the optional ones as you're up for!

What is your role? (Check as many as apply) *

- Data scientist
- Domain scientist
- Biocurator / data annotator
- Ontology developer/editor
- Tool developer
- Other...

What are some of the key ontologies you use?

Long answer text

How do you typically view ontologies?

- BioPortal / OntoPortal
- OLS
- Ontobee
- Protégé
- Within a curation interface
- Within a data portal (e.g. Model Organism Database)
- Other...

If you use ontologies programmatically, how?

- BioPortal/OntoPortal API
- OLS API
- Ontobee SPARQL
- Ubergraph SPARQL
- Software library (e.g. OAK) -- please specify which
- Other...

How important is it for you to understand changes in the main ontologies you use? For example: getting a list of terms introduced in a new release, fine-grained summaries of each release.

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